

INTERFACES IN FIBROUS ORGANIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Here the review and generalizing of author's works dealing with interfaces of fibrous organic composites are presented. Mechanisms of interface layer formation were considered. It was shown the skin layer of fiber take place important role in interface layer formation due to its sorption interaction with binder components. The interface layer was found to be that place where crack initiation could arise.

INTRODUCTION

It is known the composite properties are affected by existence of interface layer [1-4]. Its features and expanses depend on nature of filler, matrix and their interaction. Adsorption interaction between inorganic fibers and organic binder is the only possible one. Being short acting [2] it cannot affect essentially on composition and structure of matrix in spite of intensive selective adsorption. In this case the adhesion strength depends on nature of chemical bonds formed on interfaces [1,4] and matrix relaxation properties providing with decrease of internal stresses [5]. Note, the formation of expanded interface layer in composites based on inorganic fibers is possible too. However, its occurrence is connected with influence of internal stresses arising on interface in the course of composite formation structure and properties of matrix [6].

In case of polymer fibers we meet another situation. The main feature of polymer fibers is anisotropy of their structure and properties. As a consequence, the fibrillization arises under fiber straining [7]. It can display itself as plastic character of deformation [8]. The fiber structure is possible to subdivide on two parts: skin and core [9,10]. Difference of their structure and properties stipulates peculiarities of fiber rupture in composites.

The polymer nature of fiber itself allows the volume sorption interaction of binder components with fibers. As a result, the structure and properties of fiber in composite material cannot be the same as native ones. Existence of fibrillar structure and skin layer produces complex kinetic law of penetration of binder components inside fiber. That is why, the fiber properties in composites have to depend on the kinetics of material formation. In the course of volume sorption binder composition and its gradient can be change sufficiently. After curing the expanded interface layer including both modified fiber skin layer and gradient nearest matrix layer is fixed by chemical bonds.

There is every reason to study the kinetics interface layer formation to find the ways of its structure controlling. At the same time, we need to understand the role of interface layer in the process of composite fracture based on polymer fibers.

These problems were the objects of our investigations [8, 11-22]. The present paper is the review and generalizing of author's works.

SORPTION PROPERTIES OF POLYMER FIBERS

As far as the main mechanism of interface formation was supposed to be the sorption interaction of polymer fibers and binder components the investigation of sorption of low molecular substances with polymer fibers was the first and essential stage of the work.

Diffusion coefficient D , its dependence on time and sorbate concentration characterize kinetics of sorption of low molecular substances with polymer bodies. In case of structural homogeneous bodies value of D is constant during the process. The increasing of D usually is related with dependence of D on sorbate concentration. Decreasing of D is explained by slow relaxation processes in the system [23,24].

Fig.1. Sorption of water with aramide fibers: Terlon (1), Ammos (2), SVM (3).

a. Dependence of effective diffusion coefficient D/R^2 on time.

b. Dependence of specific heat E_{sp} on penetration depth, r/R .

However, in structural heterogeneous polymer bodies as polymer fibers there is another cause of changing effective D in course of the process [22]. Due to space inhomogeneity the process is characterized by set of local diffusion coefficients. The value of each of them is determined by local density. Effective D is the result of averaging of local ones.

Actually, in our investigations of sorption of water and some other low molecular sorbates with aramid and high modulus polyethylene fibers effective diffusion coefficient was found to decrease in course of the process. Some of experimental data are shown on Fig.1. Such behavior is not a consequence of fiber relaxation under sorption. It was confirmed by direct studies on fiber shrinkage in the course of sorption [25].

All curves shown on Fig.1 demonstrate that D changes abruptly in time region of 1000 s. Obviously, this phenomenon has structural nature. It is supported with data of Fig.1b. There are dependencies of specific heat E on depth of sorbate penetration. As one can see E increases up to some depths (0.1 of fiber radius). Then the increasing stops. This depth just corresponds to time of 1000 s.

The initial stage of sorption is assumed to relate to fiber skin layer. It means its thickness approximately equal to 0.1 of fiber radius. At the same time, its structure is less dense compare to fiber core ($E_{skin} < E_{core}$, $D_{skin} > D_{core}$).

Another method allowing to estimate thickness of fiber skin layer is inverse gas chromatography (IGC) [11, 12, 17]. Usually this method is used for characterization of equilibrium polymer blend or solutions. However, under conditions of IGC experiments there are true equilibrium at low temperatures (gas - surface of vitreous polymer) and at more high temperatures (gas - volume of polymer existing in rubbery elasticity state). In the transient temperature range there is no equilibrium state because of time of experiments is comparable to time of system relaxation and true equilibrium is not able to realize. In this case we cannot use thermodynamic approaches. Instead of we have to assume the equilibrium gas - polymer surface and steady state between surface and volume of polymer body [11,17,20].

Fig.2. Temperature dependence of the desorption constant K (a) and efficient surface a (b) in the inverse gas chromatography of *o*-xylene as sorbate and Terlon as sorrent covered with diethylene glycole diglycidyl ether of mass content, %: 0 (O), 0.5(■), 1.1(□), 3 (●).

In this case in transient temperature range the IGC method allows to get two parameters of fiber skin layer: effective surface a (layer thickness) and equilibrium constant K (thermodynamic layer characteristics).

Temperature dependencies of K and a for aramide fiber Terlon native and treated by epoxy binder are shown on Fig.2. As one can see above 333K effective fiber surface increases, i.e., depth of sorbate penetration increases. At the same time, effective surface a is proportional to quantity of resine cover and temperature dependence in this case has normal view: a decreases with temperature.

From these data we can evaluate the thickness of fiber skin layer: its value nearly to 0.1 of fiber radius in according to above mentioned diffusion data.

The study of polyethylene fibers using IGS method leads to similar conclusions. There is only one difference: the thickness of the skin layer depends on temperature prehistory [17,20].

Fig.3. Dependence of $tg\delta$ on temperature for aramide fibers: SVM (a), Armos (b), Terlon (c) native (1) and treated with dimethylformamide (2), diethylene glycol diglycidyl ether (3) and dibutyl phthalate (4)

It is clear interfaces in composites descent its properties from fiber skin layer ones. Therefore, they can be determined by studying sorbat effect on deformation and relaxation features of fiber skin layer. We have managed to obtain the information about relaxation state of skin layer using unconnected bunch of fibers as string of rotary pendulum. In this case just external friction between fiber surfaces is the main source of mechanical losses.

On Fig.3 there are curves of temperature dependence of mechanical losses for aramide fibers native and treated with some low molecular agents. As one can see the treatment affects a values and a shapes of picks of losses angle tangent. Observed widening and even splitting of the picks indicates the structure inhomogeneity of fiber skin layer. More clear resolving of picks means that after treatment the skin layers get more equilibrium structure.

Temperature location of main pick of skin layer of PE fibers (Fig.4) is near to 350K, i.e., much more that T_g of amorphous polymer (approximately, 150K) and lower than melting point of polymer with folding crystals (approximately, 400K). From this one can conclude that the structure of skin layer differ significantly from core one. Unfortunately, we have not any data on core relaxation properties of aramide fibers.

Therefore, we cannot to make comparisons of skin and core structures in this case.

None the less, experimental data on transversal deformation of fibers bunch [14, 15, 17] allow to suppose that skin layer possesses the more deformation ability compare to fiber core.

Fig.4. Dependence of $tg\delta$ on temperature for PE fiber native (1) and treated with toluene (2)

ROLE OF INTERFACE IN FIBROUS COMPOSITES FAILURE

In the course of composite formation skin layer of fiber transforms to interface due to sorption interaction of fiber with binder components and following curing them. A priori the role of curing process cannot be predicted. Actually, after curing the rigidity of interface layer can be either higher or lower of skin layer one. Moreover, the rigidity can decrease due to changing of binder components ratio as a result of selective sorption. That is why, we have to determine composite interface features directly.

Model composite samples were prepared [8, 13, 18, 20] as plate with fibers located in middle of it. Matrix was obtained by cure of epoxies mixture. After curing the composite samples were annealed.

Samples were deformed with strain set. The strain was managed with microscrew, arising stress was measured. The appearance and development of defects and cracks were observed with optical microscope.

Essentially, in this research we used plasticity of polymer fibers. Really, the polymer fiber are ruptured via neck formation. When it proceeds in polymer matrix the necks accumulation is

observed [8, 13]. On Fig.5 there is scheme of fiber rupture in composite for two cases: (a) when fiber has brittle character of rupture, and (b) when fiber has plastic one.

The first case is typical for glass fibers. The second type of rupture was found when aramide and PE fibers were studied [8, 13, 18]. Metallic wires are ruptured in polymer matrix in the same manner [18, 20].

The nonuniform deformation of interface layer, especially, in the neck regions is responsible for the neck arising. We have observed that cracks were initiated just near necks and propagated along fiber surface as helix. The fiber rupture can be observed at the more later stages of straining.

Fig.5. The scheme of crack initiation and propagation during process of straining of model composites with glass (a), polymer (b) and metallic (c) fibers.

These results should be interpreted as an evidence of high rigidity of interface layer in polymer fibrous composites. So, in this case just the interface layer can be the source of the cracks initiated. This feature differs the composites based on polymer fibers from glass fibrous composites: the latter breaking proceeds via fiber rupture as initiating act.

CONCLUSION

In this work we try to show the specific features of polymer fibers displaying in particular mechanism of interface layer formation in the course of composite preparing. The role of interface layer is not limited with dissipation of energy released at fiber rupture. The interface layer can be the place where cracks are initiated. This conclusion demands to put the question to refine the micromechanics of failure of polymer fibrous composites.

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